

ISic3593

I.Sicily inscription 3593

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Sicilia

Place of origin (modern)

Sicily

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἰέρωνος
2. βασιλέος
3. πωλυς τῶν
4. Ἀκραίων

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645672

EDCS 41300120

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 56.1103.3.3

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo.

Sikelika 6. Palermo. At 159*

Dimartino, A. 2006. Per una revisione dei documenti epigrafici siracusani pertinenti al regno di Ierone II. In Michelini, C.(eds.), *Guerra e pace in Sicilia e nel Mediterraneo antico (VIII-III sec. a.C.)*. Arte, prassi e teoria della pace e della guerra. Pisa. pp. 703-717. At 710 no.3.3 fig.420

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